

An improved blast-resistant rice cultivar for irrigated paddy in West Africa

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Among the several thousand cultivars introduced into West African programs since the early 1970s, the line IR1416-131-5, from the IRR1 cross Peta*4/TN1//Tetep, has proven to be both resistant to blast and excellent for irrigated conditions.

Until now, IR5 has been the most widely recommended and planted variety in irrigated swamps in Liberia. The swamps have been developed in rolling lowland terrain in a rain forest area where 1,800 to 3,000 mm of rainfall falls over an 8- to 10-month period.

Since its 1974 introduction, IR1416 has yielded better than IR5 in both wet and dry seasons in areas of Liberia where water control and soil conditions are good (see table). But IR5's yield in the wet season under poor water control or undefined imbalanced soil conditions remains superior. When sown directly at high seed rate and with fertilization (NPK, 150-50-70), IR1416 lodged moderately 2 weeks before maturity.

In Nigeria, IR1416 and BG90-2 from Sri Lanka are now the two main varieties grown at the high-technology Japanese/Nigerian irrigated rice project at Adani, Anambra state. This area is a derived savanna zone with about 1,400-mm rainfall from April to October. The objective of the project is to grow 10 t/ha per year from 2 crops — a goal reached on part of the area. Commercial yields of both IR1416 and BG90-2 have ranged from 4.5 to 5.5 t/ha. IR1416 is preferred for its blast resistance, its adaptability to direct sowing of pregerminated seeds, and its consistent performance in both dry and wet seasons. Compared with other rices, it is subject to less attack by the stem borer *Chilo zaccanius*.

IR1416 is a high-tillering spreading-type semidwarf (75–90 cm) of intermediate growth duration

Performance of IR1416 and IR5 in yield trials in Liberian irrigated inland valley swamps, 1974–77.

Year	Site	Yield (t/ha)		IR1416 yield (% of IR5)
		IR1416	IR5	
<i>Wet season, good management</i>				
1974	Suakoko	6.6	4.9	+64
1975	Suakoko	6.1	4.7	+30
1976	Suakoko	4.4	3.7	+21
1977	Voinjama	5.9	5.5	+8
	Mean	5.8	4.5	+32
<i>Wet season, poor water control^a</i>				
1975	Suakoko	3.4	3.4	+1
1977	Suakoko	3.4	5.1	-34
1977	Kolahun	3.9	5.8	-33
1977	Zlehtown	3.8	4.4	-13
	Mean	3.6	4.7	-26
<i>Dry season</i>				
1974	Suakoko	4.8	3.6	+32
1975	Foya	6.9	5.2	+33
1976	Suakoko	4.4	4.0	+10
1977	Suakoko	4.0	3.5	+15
	Mean	5.0	4.1	+23

^aNewly developed swamp, or land with imbalanced nutrition, or both.

(130–135 days). It has medium-long panicles and medium-slender grains (24 g/1,000-grain wt) that are more translucent and of better quality than those of IR5. In Liberia, IR1416 is especially preferred to IR5 because of its keeping quality after cooking. It has low levels of glume discoloration (dirty panicles), and good resistance to sheath blight, sheath rot, and leaf scald. IR1416 is moderately tolerant of iron toxicity, but susceptible to brown spot, caseworm, and rice yellow mottle virus. Blast did not attack it under the dryland, drought conditions at IITA that killed varieties such as IR5, BG90-2, and Brengut. In those trials, six major vertical genes, as indexed on japonica differentials, were present in the blast population.

In 1976, Liberia nominated IR1416 to the coordinated variety trials of the West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA). It performed well under good management in Mauritania, Mali, Upper Volta, Sierra Leone, and Ivory Coast.

IR1416 is proposed for release in Liberia as Suakoko 12. It is considered most appropriate for West African paddy with good irrigation and with nontoxic soils — especially where current cultivars are subject to neck blast. It is used as a parent in IITA's hybridization program. ■

Induction of monogenic recessive male sterility in IR36 by ethyleneimine treatment

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To facilitate rapid recombination breeding and to save labor in the hybridization program, attempts were made to induce monogenic recessive male sterility in IR36 by use of ethyleneimine, a chemical mutagen. Dried IR36 seeds were treated with ethyleneimine at various concentrations (0.2%, 0.4%, 0.8%, 1.2%, and 1.6%) for 1 hour and 3 hours. The 0.2% concentration for 3 hours depressed germination by 69%; the 0.4% concentration for 1 hour depressed it by 30%. But the 0.2% for 1 hour gave 93% germination, similar to that of the control (99%). Seeds in other treatments did not germinate.

About 2,000 plants from treatments of 0.2% for 3 hours and 4% for 1 hour were planted in M₁. A single panicle was harvested from each M₁ plant. All M₁ plants produced M₂ pedigrees. Out of 1,954 M₂ lines of 12 plants each, 93 lines segregated for sterility and partial sterility. A single plant from each line was transferred from the field to the greenhouse for study of chromosomes, pollen fertility, and cross fertility of the female organ.

The meiotic pairing and pollen fertility studies of 93 M₂ lines revealed the following information.

Meiotic behavior	Pollen fertility range (%)	Lines (no.)
Reciproval translocation	1.6–80.0	61
Triploid	0.9–2.1	2
Desynaptic plants	2.1–22.1	2
Normal meiosis	80.0	13
Meiosis not studied	33.0–89.0	6
Normal meiosis	0.0–4.0	4
Not identified		5
Total		93

Four male-sterile lines had excellent crossability with IR36. No seed set was observed after selfing but some seeds were obtained from sterile plants produced by outcrossing. All the M₃ plants were fertile. But when pollination